

The rules do not apply: an empirical and mechanistic test of Lanchester's models of combat (supplementary material)

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This document describes details of the statistical models used in the paper.

General methods

Termites were collected in the field and kept in plastic containers in an ambient lab. They were fed dead wood collected near their natural home and kept for less than two weeks each. For trials, soldiers and workers were picked arbitrarily and battles were staged between every combination of soldiers and workers. Each pairing was replicated multiple times with varying initial ratios. Battles were staged in petri dishes.

Group size analysis

As an overall test of which group (smaller or larger) had an advantage, if any, we fit two regression models in RStudio (R Studio Team, 2021) using the program R (R Core Team, 2021). Both models were binomial generalized linear mixed models (GLMM) with logit links implemented in the package `lme4` (Bates et al., 2015). Survival during a battle was coded success and death was coded as failure. The initial proportion of individuals from a colony was a fixed effect and colony identity was modeled as a random effect. The package DHARMA version 0.4.1 (Hartig, 2021) was used for residual diagnostics.

Model 1

In model 1, the only random effect was the intercept term (subscripts omitted for simplicity):

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0^{(k)} + \beta_1 x$$
$$p(y) = \binom{n}{y} p^y (1-p)^{n-y},$$

where k indexes the focal colony ($k = 1, 2, \dots, 6$, colony order C, D, F, G, I, N), x is the proportion of fighters from the focal colony (0.2, 0.5, 0.8), p is the probability of survival for an individual from colony k given starting fraction x , and y is the observed number of survivors. The starting number of fighters is $n = 50x$.

Diagnostic plots/tests from the DHARMA package are shown in Figure S1. The scale residual QQ plot (Figure S1a) does not show a significant departure from expectation and box plots for each level of initial proportion (Figure S1b) show expected results except for the 0.5 proportion, which includes too many low residuals. Because battles were allowed to run until one army had zero survivors, the data show an excess of battles in which there were zero survivors, which is not well predicted by the binomial model. Figure S1c demonstrates that observed residuals fall within the distribution of residuals using model M1. Figure S1d shows the data (points) and regression lines from model 1.

AIC was 216.9 and BIC was 222.8 for this model.

Model 2

In model 2, both intercept and slope were random effects (subscripts omitted for simplicity):

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0^{(k)} + \beta_1^{(k)}x$$

$$p(y) = \binom{n}{y}p^y(1-p)^{n-y},$$

where k , x , p , and y are defined as in model 1. AIC was 212.9 and BIC was 222.9 for this model. Allowing random slopes (Model 2) improved AIC but led to a slightly worse BIC compared to Model 1. Model 1 was preferred because of its slightly better BIC. DHARMA diagnostics for model 2 (not shown) were nearly identical to those for model 1.

(a) Scaled residual QQ plot

(b) Box plots of PIT (probability integral transform) residuals for each of the three fighter proportions (0.2, 0.5, 0.8)

(c) Simulated (histogram) vs. fitted (red line) residuals

(d) Probability of survival based on initial proportion of total fighters, colored by colony

Figure S1: Diagnostics from the DHARMa package and graphical summary of results for Group Size Model 1.

Behavioral analysis

Video analysis was performed by many undergraduate students (listed in acknowledgements section in the paper). Quality control was performed by randomly spot-checking parts of videos. Student data needed at least 95% accuracy to be used for analysis. The program PotPlayer (<https://potplayer.en.softonic.com/>) was used to watch videos frame-by-frame.

Table S1 shows the number and proportion of attacks at the mandibles (segment A) and the body (segment B) for individuals at varying initial ratios (N=90 individuals for all initial ratios).

Table S1: Attack statistics

Count	Initial 10	Initial 25	Initial 40
Segment A	1037	895	587
Segment B	1615	481	103
Total bites	2652	1376	690
A mean proportion	0.391	0.650	0.851
B mean proportion	0.609	0.350	0.149
Variance (for both)	0.017	0.038	0.030
Total bites per termite	29.47	15.29	7.67

To determine which part of the body a termite was most likely to receive an attack based on that individual’s initial group proportion, we tested 2 generalized linear mixed model (GLMM) regressions. Both models are binomial GLMMs where an attack at the mandibles is a “success” and an attack on the rest of the body is a “failure.” The logit probability of the placement of an attack is regressed on the focal individual’s initial group proportion. Model 1 has a random effect of “Pair” (i.e. CD, FG, or IN) and model 2 has a random effect of “Colony” (i.e. C, D, F, G, I, N). These models were analyzed with RStudio (R Studio Team, 2021) using R version 4.0.4 (R Core Team, 2021) using the package lme4 (Bates et al., 2015).

Model 1

The same GLMM template was used for both models; the models differed only in the meaning of k :

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0^{(k)} + \beta_1 x$$
$$p(y) = \binom{n}{y} p^y (1-p)^{n-y}.$$

In model 1, the intercept varied by pair and thus k indexes the focal pair ($k = 1, 2, 3$, pair order CD, FG, IN), x is the proportion of fighters from the individual's colony (0.2, 0.5, 0.8), p is the probability that an individual is attacked at the mandibles (as opposed to the body) given starting fraction x , and y is the observed number of attacks targeting the mandibles, with $p(y)$ denoting the probability of y head-on attacks given p . The total number of attacks is n .

AIC was 1174.3 and BIC was 1185.1 for this model.

Model 2

In model 2, the intercept varied by colony, in which case k indexes the focal colony ($k = 1, 2, \dots, 6$, colony order C, D, F, G, I, N). The quantities x , p , y , and n are as defined above for model 1.

AIC was 1170.9 and BIC was 1181.6 for this model.

Model 2 had a lower AIC and BIC and thus is preferred over model 1.

Diagnostic plots/tests from the DHARMA package are shown in Figure S2. The scale residual QQ plot (Figure S2a) shows a significant departure from expectation (KS test and outlier tests) but box plots for each level of initial proportion (Figure S2b) show the expected results. Because battles were allowed to run until one army had zero survivors, we suggest that the significant KS and outlier tests are due to an excess of battles in which there were zero survivors, which is not well predicted by the binomial model. Figure S2c demonstrates that observed residuals fall within the distribution of residuals using model M1.

(a) Scaled residual QQ plot

(b) Box plots of PIT (probability integral transform) residuals for each of the three fighter proportions (0.2, 0.5, 0.8)

(c) Simulated (histogram) vs. fitted (red line) residuals

(d) Probability of a head-on attack based on initial proportion of total fighters, colored by colony

Figure S2: Diagnostics from the DHARMA package and graphical summary of results for Behavior Model 2.

AMG Model

We used a Bayesian implementation of the AMG model to analyze the number of deaths each colony endured every five minutes. By testing the AMG model, we also tested the Lanchester models, because they are a subset of the AMG model. The quantity R was defined as the ratio of individual fighting ability of group 2 (group N in the paper) to that of group 1 (group M in the paper) between the two sides (i.e. $R = \alpha_N/\alpha_M$). When $R = 1$, individual fighting ability was considered equivalent. We carried out analyses in which R was either fixed to one or allowed to vary. The AMG parameter λ was always fixed to one. Separate analyses were carried out for each starting proportion separately as well as for all three starting proportions combined. Two methods were used to compare model performance: marginal likelihood (MargL) estimated using the generalized steppingstone method (Fan et al., 2011) and the posterior-predictive Gelfand-Ghosh (GG) approach (Gelfand and Ghosh, 1998).

Software availability

All analyses were carried out using software freely available from

<https://github.com/plewis/termite-battle>.

This software can be used to obtain posterior samples, marginal likelihood estimates, and Gelfand-Ghosh posterior predictive analyses using the AMG model. The data file used with the termite battle software is *battle.dat*, which is also provided in the supplementary material.

Data

The data comprise observations of the number of combatants from each of two termite armies still alive after 5 minute time intervals called *epochs*. Figure S3 shows data from a battle comprising 3 epochs. The army depicted on top (group 1) begins with 30 combatants and was observed to have 24, 20, and 19 combatants at times 5, 10, and 15, respectively. The army depicted on bottom (group 2) begins with 20 combatants and was observed to have 12, 2, and 0 combatants at times 5, 10, and 15, respectively. The battle ends when one army is reduced to 0 combatants (or stopped arbitrarily if termites stop fighting).

Lanchester-like model

Figure S3: Example involving a battle comprising 3 epochs. Inset shows notation for epoch $k = 3$.

The AMG model was described by Adams and Mesterton-Gibbons (2003). Our Bayesian implementation of the AMG model differs from that in Plowes and Adams (2005) primarily in that Plowes and Adams used simulation to approximate the likelihood whereas, in this paper, data augmentation is used so that the likelihood need not be approximated. Data augmentation involves the introduction of latent variables representing the time of each death. These death times are integrated out during MCMC.

In the AMG model, the differential equations defining the progress of the battle are

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -\alpha_1^{1-\lambda} \alpha_2 n m^{2-\theta} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = -\alpha_1 \alpha_2^{1-\lambda} m n^{2-\theta}, \quad (2)$$

where the values m is the current number of combatants in group 1, n is the current number of combatants in group 2, α_1 is the individual fighting ability of group 1, α_2 is the individual fighting ability of group 2, θ determines the dependence of group fighting ability on a group's own numbers, and λ determines the dependence of group fighting ability on the group's individual fighting ability.

At any time during the battle, we expect (Appendix S1)

$$R = \frac{m_0^\theta - m^\theta}{n_0^\theta - n^\theta} = \left(\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1} \right)^\lambda \quad (3)$$

Following Plowes and Adams (2005), we consider only $\lambda = 1$, leading to these simpler expressions:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -R\alpha_1 n m^{2-\theta} \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dn}{dt} = -\alpha_1 m n^{2-\theta}. \quad (5)$$

Plowes and Adams (2005) define the **group fighting abilities** as (Appendix S2)

$$\alpha_1^\lambda m^\theta \quad \text{group 1} \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha_2^\lambda n^\theta \quad \text{group 2} \quad (7)$$

“The group with the greater fighting ability has the lower *per capita* death rate and will eliminate the other group in a fully escalated fight.” (Plowes and Adams, 2005).

The value $\theta = 2$ corresponds to **Lanchester’s square law** (expected when members of a larger group can concentrate attacks on members of a smaller group, leading to group fighting ability proportional to the square of the number of combatants in the group but linearly related to individual fighting ability) and $\theta = 1$ corresponds to **Lanchester’s linear law** (expected when members of the larger group do not concentrate attacks on members of the smaller group, leading to group fighting ability rising linearly with both group size and individual fighting ability).

Because the starting and ending number of combatants are known for each epoch, each epoch is conditionally independent of other epochs given the model parameters α , R , and θ .

Latent variables

Latent variables are introduced to represent the times at which every death occurred. These variables are shown as tick marks (hereafter ticks) above or below the time line in Figure S3. Note that there are 6 ticks (one for each death) above the line between the starting army size of 30 and the 24 survivors at the end of the first epoch.

The inset in Figure S3 illustrates the notation used for a single epoch. The variables t_1 , t_2 , and t_3 represent times of deaths, where t_2 is the time of the 1 death in group 1, and t_1 and t_3 are the times of the 2 deaths in group 2. The variables t_0 and t_4 represent fixed time endpoints for the epoch.

A secondary notation is needed when updating death times because each time is group-specific and is thus governed by a group-specific rate. Deaths in group 1 for epoch k are denoted (in Figure S3 inset) $t_{k,0}^{(1)} \cdots t_{k,2}^{(1)}$, while deaths in group 2 are denoted $t_{n,0}^{(2)} \cdots t_{n,3}^{(2)}$.

When, for example, $t_{k,1}^{(2)}$ is updated, its new proposed position must lie between $t_{k,0}^{(2)}$ and $t_{k,2}^{(2)}$ because the update is conditional on current values of all other model parameters, including latent variables (Metropolis within Gibbs sampling). Note that the position of $t_{k,1}^{(2)}$ is not constrained by deaths in the other group, such as $t_{k,1}^{(1)}$; however, moving $t_{k,1}^{(2)}$ to the right of $t_{k,1}^{(1)}$ would affect death rates in both groups and thus would also affect the likelihood.

In practice, $t_{k,1}^{(2)}$ is discouraged by the prior from getting too close to its neighbors $t_{k,0}^{(2)}$ and $t_{k,2}^{(2)}$ by the presence of “spacer” ticks (shown in Figure S3 inset by triangles) that lie between each pair of deaths, preventing two ticks from the same group having exactly the same time. This is discussed in more detail in the section on priors.

Likelihood

The likelihood for epoch k involves the product of terms associated with time intervals (sojourn times) between deaths. For example, in the Figure S3 inset, consider the interval between the first death in group 2, $t_{k,1} = t_{k,1}^{(2)}$, and the first death in group 1, $t_{k,2} = t_{k,1}^{(1)}$. The probability that no death occurred in group 1 over the interval of length $t_{k,2} - t_{k,1}$ is

$$e^{-R\alpha_1 n_{k,2} m_{k,2}^{2-\theta} (t_{k,2} - t_{k,1})}, \quad (8)$$

the probability that no death occurred in group 2 over the same interval is

$$e^{-\alpha_1 m_{k,2} n_{k,2}^{2-\theta} (t_{k,2} - t_{k,1})}, \quad (9)$$

so the probability that no death occurred in either group from time $t_{k,1}$ to $t_{k,2}$ is

$$e^{-\mu_{k,2}(t_{k,2} - t_{k,1})} = e^{-(R\alpha_1 n_{k,2} m_{k,2}^{2-\theta} + \alpha_1 m_{k,2} n_{k,2}^{2-\theta})(t_{k,2} - t_{k,1})}, \quad (10)$$

where $m_{k,2}$ and $n_{k,2}$ are the number of combatants in group 1 and group 2 during the sojourn $t_{k,1}$ to $t_{k,2}$, respectively. The probability (density) of the (group 1) death that terminates the interval is the instantaneous group 1 death rate,

$$R\alpha_1 n_{k,2} m_{k,2}^{2-\theta}. \quad (11)$$

The *numerator* of the likelihood over all K epochs can now be specified:

$$p(y_1, y_2, \mathbf{t}^{(1)}, \mathbf{t}^{(2)} | \alpha, R, \theta, T) = \quad (12)$$

$$= \prod_{k=1}^K e^{-\mu_{k,S_k+1}(t_{k,S_k+1}-t_{k,S_k})} \quad (13)$$

$$\cdot \prod_{i=1}^{S_k} e^{-\mu_{k,i}(t_{k,i}-t_{k,i-1})} \left[\delta_{k,i} r_{k,i}^{(2)} + (1 - \delta_{k,i}) r_{k,i}^{(1)} \right], \quad (14)$$

where y_1 and y_2 are the number of deaths suffered by groups 1 and 2, respectively, $\mathbf{t}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{t}^{(2)}$ are the vectors of death times (each defined on the interval $[0, T]$ minutes) in groups 1 and 2, respectively, S_k is the total number of deaths in epoch k , and

$$r_{k,i}^{(1)} = R\alpha_1 n_{k,i} m_{k,i}^{2-\theta} \quad (15)$$

$$r_{k,i}^{(2)} = \alpha_1 m_{k,i} n_{k,i}^{2-\theta} \quad (16)$$

$$\delta_{k,i} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{death } i \text{ in epoch } k \text{ is in group 2} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

The *denominator* of the likelihood is the joint prior on death times, $p(\mathbf{t}^{(1)}, \mathbf{t}^{(2)} | T)$, which is defined below in the section ‘‘Joint prior on group-specific death times’’.

The overall likelihood (over all epochs) is thus

$$L = p(y_1, y_2 | \mathbf{t}^{(1)}, \mathbf{t}^{(2)}, \alpha, R, \theta, T) = \frac{p(y_1, y_2, \mathbf{t}^{(1)}, \mathbf{t}^{(2)} | \alpha, R, \theta, T)}{p(\mathbf{t}^{(1)}, \mathbf{t}^{(2)} | T)}. \quad (18)$$

Remark. *It may seem to make no sense to divide by the joint prior on death times because this term will be canceled out during MCMC when the likelihood is multiplied by the same joint prior on death times to form the posterior. If the marginal likelihood is being estimated, however, it is important to include the denominator in order to correctly compute the likelihood; the marginal likelihood will be incorrect if it does not condition on all parameters.*

Priors

Priors for α , R , θ , and λ

The parameters α , R , and θ are all assigned vague Lognormal prior distributions with parameters $\mu = 0$ and $\sigma = 100$.

$$p(\alpha) = \frac{1}{\alpha\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\log(\alpha)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (19)$$

$$p(R) = \frac{1}{R\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\log(R)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (20)$$

$$p(\theta) = \frac{1}{\theta\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\log(\theta)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (21)$$

$$p(\lambda) = \frac{1}{\lambda\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{(\log(\lambda)-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (22)$$

Remark. *Plowes and Adams (2005) used $N(\mu = 2, \sigma = 10000)$ for θ ; however, we have no reason to believe that θ can be negative and have thus used a prior with support restricted to the positive reals.*

Joint prior on group-specific death times

The j death times (in *either* group 1 or group 2) are modeled as the even-numbered order statistics of $2j + 1$ total order statistics (the odd-numbered points represent spacers). The joint prior on death times for one particular group is thus a $(j + 1)$ -dimensional Dirichlet distribution in which every parameter equals 2, transformed to the time scale of an epoch, namely $T = 5$. This involves multiplying each individual Dirichlet-distributed time by T , yielding a Jacobian term equal to $1/T^j$.

For example, the joint prior for the $j = 2$ death times in group 2 for the epoch in the inset of Figure S3 would be:

$$p(t_{k,1}^{(2)}, t_{k,2}^{(2)}) = \left(\frac{1}{T^2}\right) \left(\frac{2!}{1! 1!}\right) \left(t_{k,1}^{(2)} - t_{k,0}^{(2)}\right)^{2-1} \left(t_{k,2}^{(2)} - t_{k,1}^{(2)}\right)^{2-1} \left(t_{k,3}^{(2)} - t_{k,2}^{(2)}\right)^{2-1} \quad (23)$$

The joint prior for all death times in a particular epoch is the product of the death time prior for each of the two groups, and the total joint prior is the product of these epoch-specific death time priors. More explanation is provided in Appendix S3.

Figure S4: Scatterplot of $\log(\theta)$ (y-axis) vs. $\log(\alpha)$ (x-axis) showing strong correlation. Red arrows show 50 successful updates using the bivariate proposal with $\rho = 0.9$.

MCMC details

The parameter λ was always fixed to the value 1 and thus never updated in our study.

Updating R involves straightforward use of a centered-window proposal with reflection. Given current value R_0 , a proposed new value R is chosen uniformly within a window of width δ_R centered over R_0 as follows:

$$R = R_0 - \delta_R/2 + u\delta_R, \quad (24)$$

where $u \sim U(0, 1)$ and δ_R is the window width. If the proposed value $R < 0$, then R is multiplied by -1 to reflect back into the support of the Lognormal prior distribution.

In practice, α and θ are strongly correlated (Figure S4), so a bivariate normal proposal distribution is used to update both simultaneously. Assuming that the joint probability of the point (z_1, z_2) is bivariate normal with mean $(0, 0)$ and variance-covariance matrix

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_1^2 & \rho\sigma_1\sigma_2 \\ \rho\sigma_1\sigma_2 & \sigma_2^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

Given current point (α_0, θ_0) , let

$$\alpha = e^{\log(\alpha_0)+z_1} \quad (26)$$

$$\theta = e^{\log(\theta_0)+z_2} \quad (27)$$

such that

$$\alpha_0 = \alpha e^{-z_1} \quad (28)$$

$$\theta_0 = \theta e^{-z_2} \quad (29)$$

This proposal is not symmetric due to the transformation to and from log scale, so the Hastings ratio is needed.

$$f(\alpha, \theta) = f(\alpha_0, \theta_0) \begin{vmatrix} \frac{\partial \alpha_0}{\partial \alpha} & \frac{\partial \theta_0}{\partial \alpha} \\ \frac{\partial \alpha_0}{\partial \theta} & \frac{\partial \theta_0}{\partial \theta} \end{vmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$= f(\alpha_0, \theta_0) e^{-(z_1+z_2)}. \quad (31)$$

The Hastings ratio is thus:

$$\frac{f(\alpha_0, \theta_0)}{f(\alpha, \theta)} = e^{z_1+z_2} \quad (32)$$

Updating the time of death j for one particular group in one particular epoch involves proposing a new position uniformly between the time of death $j - 1$ and the time of death $j + 1$ (note that either $j - 1$ or $j + 1$ could represent an endpoint of the epoch). This proposal is symmetric and thus the Hastings ratio equals 1.

Results

Table S2 and Table S3 provide parameter estimates, marginal likelihoods, and Gelfand-Ghosh measures for all AMG analyses conducted. Below is a description of each column:

Column	Description
Pair	The focal colony pair. All means data from all colony pairs and all starting ratios were combined.
Ratio	The numbers of starting individuals from each army. 1040 for pair CD means colony C began with 10 fighters and colony D with 40. All means all ratios combined for a given colony pair.
Epochs	The number of 5-minute epochs recorded. The number of epochs varied depending on how fast the losing army reached zero fighters.
Fixed	Whether parameters were fixed ($R = 1, \theta = 0, \theta = 1$) or all parameters were allowed to vary (none).
log(MargL)	The log of the marginal likelihood for this case. Larger values are better.
GG_p	Gelfand-Ghosh predictive variance component. Smaller values are better because they mean that a model is less variable in its predictions.
GG_g	Gelfand-Ghosh goodness-of-fit component. Smaller values are better because they mean that a model predicts data that is closer to being centered on the original data.
GG	Combined measure. Smaller is better because it means that a model balances predictive variance and goodness-of-fit better than a competing model.
R	Estimated value of R in the AMG model. R is the ratio α_N/α_M of individual fighting abilities.
θ	Estimated value of θ in the AMG model. θ is the exponent that determines where one is located on the Lancaster spectrum: 1 corresponds to the Lanchester linear law; 2 the Lanchester square law.
α_M	The individual fighting ability of the first colony listed in the Pair column. The individual fighting ability of the second colony listed is $\alpha_N = R\alpha_M$.

Note that the only model comparisons (using either marginal likelihood or Gelfand-Ghosh) that are comparable are those in which the data are identical. Thus, it is valid to compare marginal likelihoods or Gelfand-Ghosh measures for fixed R vs. variable

R for a given starting ratio and colony pair, but not across starting ratios or colony pairs.

Table S2: Marginal likelihoods, Gelfand-Ghosh statistics, and parameter estimates from AMG analyses (part 1).

Pair	Ratio	Epochs	Fixed	$\log(\text{MargL})$	GG_p	GG_g	GG	R	θ	α_M
All	All	203	$R = 1$	-625.10729	489.41950	801.11104	889.97502	1.00000	1.70306	0.01048
All	All	203	none	-624.87887	492.57578	801.13168	893.14162	1.03322	1.70208	0.01031
All	All	203	$\theta = 1$	-724.08799	517.48928	1034.13037	1034.55446	0.95586	1.00000	0.00183
All	All	203	$\theta = 2$	-675.90420	429.47724	872.29101	865.62274	1.03534	2.00000	0.01794
CD	All	64	$R = 1$	-182.47551	151.92862	190.88127	247.36926	1.00000	1.73303	0.01063
CD	All	64	none	-182.49139	153.85561	191.87548	249.79335	0.99666	1.73312	0.01070
CD	All	64	$\theta = 1$	-212.17511	161.69756	282.51301	302.95407	0.87209	1.00000	0.00180
CD	All	64	$\theta = 2$	-193.45606	132.14192	213.83390	239.05887	0.99493	2.00000	0.01701
CD	2525	38	$R = 1$	-129.89402	113.39956	143.27568	185.03740	1.00000	1.81133	0.01560
CD	2525	38	none	-129.71920	115.00542	142.72188	186.36636	0.90950	1.80376	0.01609
CD	2525	38	$\theta = 1$	-136.21411	101.48588	161.56197	182.26687	0.81035	1.00000	0.00187
CD	2525	38	$\theta = 2$	-124.75675	111.43177	148.80597	185.83476	0.96141	2.00000	0.02432
FG	All	59	$R = 1$	-194.63159	161.35128	238.05095	280.37676	1.00000	1.52379	0.01039
FG	All	59	none	-193.79010	164.55951	227.30095	278.20998	1.22002	1.52310	0.00940
FG	All	59	$\theta = 1$	-207.93931	172.26041	303.00672	323.76377	1.21220	1.00000	0.00263
FG	All	59	$\theta = 2$	-218.74476	130.28107	340.17596	300.36905	1.23275	2.00000	0.02233
FG	2525	37	$R = 1$	-132.23927	127.74435	149.73902	202.61386	1.00000	1.59008	0.01579
FG	2525	37	none	-132.20903	130.16863	147.95049	204.14387	1.06300	1.58070	0.01532
FG	2525	37	$\theta = 1$	-132.23154	109.16487	143.32264	180.82619	1.25412	1.00000	0.00294
FG	2525	37	$\theta = 2$	-129.78395	132.92546	187.22844	226.53967	0.88259	2.00000	0.04281
IN	All	80	$R = 1$	-256.29055	177.37912	251.41652	303.08738	1.00000	1.74237	0.00926
IN	All	80	none	-255.99577	179.37035	247.67269	303.20669	0.90564	1.74087	0.00971
IN	All	80	$\theta = 1$	-287.50576	181.57893	331.60702	347.38245	0.83331	1.00000	0.00147
IN	All	80	$\theta = 2$	-263.97248	159.19307	248.28775	283.33694	0.89592	2.00000	0.01614
IN	2525	53	$R = 1$	-183.07637	119.47070	157.10835	198.02487	1.00000	1.91106	0.01327
IN	2525	53	none	-183.05946	120.62315	157.65602	199.45115	1.05021	1.91217	0.01309
IN	2525	53	$\theta = 1$	-197.67287	110.67906	173.56471	197.46141	0.76448	1.00000	0.00125
IN	2525	53	$\theta = 2$	-175.64141	118.53694	157.42601	197.24995	1.09343	2.00000	0.01580

Table S3: Marginal likelihoods, Gelfand-Ghosh statistics, and parameter estimates from AMG analyses (part 2).

Pair	Ratio	Epochs	Fixed	$\log(\text{MargL})$	GG_p	GG_g	GG	R	θ	α_M
CD	1040	15	$R = 1$	-35.01798	23.37089	24.35575	35.54876	1.00000	1.67866	0.00925
CD	1040	15	none	-27.06947	14.81876	5.83532	17.73642	202.14700	0.71282	0.00012
CD	4010	11	$R = 1$	-38.41105	27.24055	21.77987	38.13049	1.00000	1.85326	0.00890
CD	4010	11	none	-35.14021	24.37437	16.35396	32.55136	0.10682	1.45613	0.00599
FG	1040	9	$R = 1$	-38.31369	22.13299	60.82163	52.54380	1.00000	1.73145	0.01249
FG	1040	9	none	-28.22555	10.76778	17.10300	19.31928	341.65683	0.35561	0.00006
FG	4010	13	$R = 1$	-41.26880	27.97736	31.14714	43.55093	1.00000	1.59350	0.00766
FG	4010	13	none	-38.04247	22.48039	15.72206	30.34142	0.14912	0.73049	0.00282
IN	1040	16	$R = 1$	-48.29905	33.47612	28.84712	47.89969	1.00000	1.44535	0.00551
IN	1040	16	none	-47.84844	32.34756	28.01278	46.35395	2.32753	1.24207	0.00340
IN	4010	11	$R = 1$	-43.890810	30.21583	47.79379	54.11273	1.00000	1.54488	0.00892
IN	4010	11	none	-43.432010	28.64702	46.37605	51.83504	0.66088	1.37096	0.00739

Figure S5 shows marginal posterior distributions of key parameters for the analyses corresponding to the first two lines in Table S2.

Figure S5: Parameter estimates from the AMG model. The vertical gray bars indicate the upper and lower limits of 95% credible intervals and the vertical black lines indicate the mean and median. A) θ when R is unconstrained (credible interval = 1.61-1.79; mean = median = 1.7). B) R (credible interval = 0.87-1.21; mean = median = 1.03). C) θ when R is fixed to 1.0 (credible interval = 1.61-1.79; mean = median = 1.7).

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Appendix S1: Derivation of equation 3

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dm}{dt} &= -\alpha_1^{1-\lambda} \alpha_2 n m^{2-\theta} & \frac{dn}{dt} &= -\alpha_1 \alpha_2^{1-\lambda} m n^{2-\theta} \\
 \frac{dm}{dn} &= \frac{\frac{dm}{dt}}{\frac{dn}{dt}} \\
 &= \alpha_1^{-\lambda} \alpha_2^\lambda n^{\theta-1} m^{-(\theta-1)} \\
 &= \left(\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1}\right)^\lambda \frac{n^{\theta-1}}{m^{\theta-1}} \\
 m^{\theta-1} dm &= \left(\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1}\right)^\lambda n^{\theta-1} dn \\
 \int m^{\theta-1} dm &= \left(\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1}\right)^\lambda \int n^{\theta-1} dn \\
 \left(\frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_1}\right)^\lambda &= \frac{\int m^{\theta-1} dm}{\int n^{\theta-1} dn} \\
 &= \frac{\frac{1}{\theta} [m^\theta]_{m_0}^{m_t}}{\frac{1}{\theta} [n^\theta]_{n_0}^{n_t}} \\
 &= \frac{m_t^\theta - m_0^\theta}{n_t^\theta - n_0^\theta} \\
 &= \frac{m_0^\theta - m_t^\theta}{n_0^\theta - n_t^\theta}
 \end{aligned}$$

Appendix S2: Derivation of group fighting abilities

The fighting abilities in equation 6 and equation 7 are based on *per capita* death rates.

The *per capita* death rate of group 1 is

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{1}{m} \frac{dm}{dt} &= -\frac{\alpha_2 n m^{2-\theta}}{m} \\
 &= -\alpha_2 n m^{1-\theta}
 \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, the *per capita* death rate of group 2 is

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{1}{n} \frac{dn}{dt} &= -\frac{\alpha_1 m n^{2-\theta}}{n} \\ &= -\alpha_1 m n^{1-\theta}\end{aligned}$$

The ratio of these *per capita* death rates is

$$\frac{\frac{1}{m} \frac{dm}{dt}}{\frac{1}{n} \frac{dn}{dt}} = \frac{-\alpha_2 n m^{1-\theta}}{-\alpha_1 m n^{1-\theta}} = \frac{\alpha_2 m^{-\theta}}{\alpha_1 n^{-\theta}} = \frac{\alpha_2 n^\theta}{\alpha_1 m^\theta}$$

If group 1 has the higher *per capita* death rate, then $\alpha_2 n^\theta > \alpha_1 m^\theta$. Likewise, if group 2 has the higher *per capita* death rate, then $\alpha_1 m^\theta > \alpha_2 n^\theta$. Thus, it makes sense to define the group fighting ability of group 1 as $\alpha_1 m^\theta$ and that of group 2 as $\alpha_2 n^\theta$. Note that group fighting ability can change over time as fighting ability is defined in terms of m and n , which change during the fight.

Appendix S3: Uniform order statistics

The prior on group-specific death times is based on uniform order statistics. First consider the distribution of the order statistic U_3 in Figure S6. Let $p_{U_3}(s)$ be the probability density of the third point being located at exactly s . This is tantamount to the probability that 2, 1, and 5 points fall in the intervals $(0, s)$, $(s, s + ds)$, and

Figure S6: $n = 8$ points randomly sampled from a Uniform(0,1) distribution.

$(s + ds, 1)$, respectively:

$$p_{U_3}(s)ds = \frac{8!}{2!1!5!}(s - 0)^2(ds)^1(1 - s)^5 \quad (33)$$

$$p_{U_3}(s) = \frac{8!}{2!5!}s^2(1 - s)^5 \quad (34)$$

$$p_{U_3}(s) = \frac{\Gamma(9)}{\Gamma(3)\Gamma(6)}s^{3-1}(1 - s)^{6-1} \sim \text{Beta}(3, 6). \quad (35)$$

In general, the k th order statistic $U_k \sim \text{Beta}(k, n + 1 - k)$.

Consider the joint distribution of the two order statistics U_3 and U_7 in Figure S6. Let $p_{U_3, U_7}(s, t)$ be the probability (density) that the 3rd and 7th points occur at s and t , respectively. This is tantamount to the probability that 2, 1, 3, 1, and 1 points fall in the intervals $0, s, s, s + ds, s + ds, t, t, t + dt$, and $t + dt, 1$, respectively.

$$p_{U_3, U_7}(s, t)dsdt = \frac{8!}{2!1!3!1!1!1!}(s - 0)^2(ds)^1(t - s)^3(dt)^1(1 - t)^1 \quad (36)$$

$$p_{U_3, U_7}(s, t) = \frac{8!}{2!3!1!}s^2(t - s)^3(1 - t) \quad (37)$$

$$p_{U_3, U_7}(s, t) = \frac{\Gamma(9)}{\Gamma(3)\Gamma(4)\Gamma(2)}s^{3-1}(t - s)^{4-1}(1 - t)^{2-1} \sim \text{Dir}(3, 4, 2). \quad (38)$$

In general, the j th and k th order statistics have joint distribution $U_j, U_k \sim \text{Dir}(j, k - j, n + 1 - k)$.

Joint density of all death times for a specific group

Given the previous discussion, the joint density of all n order statistics is surprisingly simple:

$$p(U_1, U_2, \dots, U_n) = n! \quad (39)$$

If the length of the interval is T rather than 1, then the uniform order statistic density must be transformed:

$$V = UT \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{dU}{dV} = \frac{1}{T} \quad (41)$$

$$p_V(v) = (1/T)p_U(v/T) \quad (42)$$

Transformed to a $[0, T]$ scale, the joint density of all n order statistics becomes:

$$p(V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n) = \frac{n!}{T^n}, \quad (43)$$

where $V_i = TU_i$.

Full-conditional prior distribution for a single death time

Assume that the tick marks representing deaths within a particular group as well as the spacers between the tick marks are each uniformly distributed points p_j between 0 and T , the length of the epoch. The i th tick mark is thus the $j = (2i)$ th point. Assume that the joint prior of the $(i - 1)$ th, i th, and $(i + 1)$ th ticks is thus the joint probability density of the $(j - 2)$ th, j th, and $(j + 2)$ th uniform order statistics:

$$p(U_{j-2}, U_j, U_{j+2}) = \text{Dir}(j - 2, j - (j - 2), (j + 2) - j, n + 1 - (j + 2)) \quad (44)$$

$$= \frac{\Gamma(n + 1)}{\Gamma(j - 2) \Gamma(2) \Gamma(2) \Gamma(n - j - 1)} \quad (45)$$

$$\cdot (U_{j-2})^{j-3} (U_j - U_{j-2})^1 (U_{j+2} - U_j)^1 (1 - U_{j+2})^{n-j-2} \quad (46)$$

$$= \frac{n!}{(j - 3)! (n - j - 2)!} \quad (47)$$

$$\cdot (U_{j-2})^{j-3} (U_j - U_{j-2}) (U_{j+2} - U_j) (1 - U_{j+2})^{n-j-2} \quad (48)$$

$$= C (U_j - U_{j-2}) (U_{j+2} - U_j) \quad (49)$$

Terms not including U_j are subsumed in the constant C . These terms include the Jacobian for a transformation to the interval $[0, T]$.

The full-conditional prior on a group-specific death time (e.g. $t_{k,i}^{(1)}$) depends only on the the times of the previous and next death in the same group (e.g. $t_{k,i-1}^{(1)}$ and $t_{k,i+1}^{(1)}$):

$$p(t_{k,i}^{(1)}) = C \left(t_{k,i}^{(1)} - t_{k,i-1}^{(1)} \right) \left(t_{k,i+1}^{(1)} - t_{k,i}^{(1)} \right), \quad (50)$$

where C is a constant. A corresponding prior is applied to group N .

Probability of one particular ordering of death times in two groups

Consider a battle epoch in which group 0 suffers $d_0 = 3$ deaths and group 1 suffers $d_1 = 2$ deaths. What is the probability of one particular ordering of these 5 deaths under the prior, which assumes death times occur independently in the two groups and

group-specific death times follow odd-numbered order statistics (due to the presence of “spacers” between each death time (see Fig. S3). Determining probabilities of orderings is important for testing whether MCMC software is correctly implementing this prior. There are $(d_0 + d_1)$ choose d_0 possible orderings. In the example above, the 10 possible orderings (5 choose 3) are shown below along with their expected and observed proportions from a sample of size 100,000 obtained by running the MCMC software written for this study under the prior. The 3 deaths in group 0 are indicated in each ordering by an asterisk (*) and the 2 deaths in group 1 are indicated by a period (.).

pattern	observed	expected	obs-exp
***..	0.04586	0.04545	0.00041
**.*.	0.11612	0.11616	-0.00004
**..*	0.08525	0.08586	-0.00061
*.**.	0.12809	0.12626	0.00183
..*	0.17680	0.17678	0.00002
*..**	0.08635	0.08586	0.00049
.***.	0.07510	0.07576	-0.00066
.**.*	0.12628	0.12626	0.00002
.*.**	0.11494	0.11616	-0.00122
..***	0.04521	0.04545	-0.00024
		1.00000	1.00000

The expected proportions were computed using numerical integration in Mathematica (Wolfram Research, Inc., 2021). For example, consider the pattern $*.**.$, which has expected proportion 0.12626. Fig. S7a shows the three group 0 deaths on top (labeled by their times r , t , and u) and the two group 1 deaths on bottom (labeled by their times s and v). Spacer events are shown as filled triangles. This ordering stipulates that $r \leq s \leq t \leq u \leq v$. The joint probability distributions for deaths in both armies are Dirichlet distributions with parameters determined by the number of (spacer) events between each death:

$$p(r, t, u) = \frac{7!}{1! 1! 1! 1! 1! 1! 1!} (r - 0)^1 (t - r)^1 (u - t)^1 (1 - u)^1 \quad (51)$$

$$p(s, v) = \frac{5!}{1! 1! 1! 1! 1!} (s - 0)^1 (v - s)^1 (1 - v)^1 \quad (52)$$

The probability of this ordering is thus

$$\Pr(*.**.) = \Pr(r \leq s \leq t \leq u \leq v) \quad (53)$$

$$= \int_0^1 \int_0^v \int_0^u \int_0^t \int_0^s p(r, t, u) p(s, v) dr ds dt du dv = 0.12626 \quad (54)$$

For the ordering *****..** (Fig. S7b), it suffices to consider just two times: let s be the time of the third death in group 0 and let t be the time of the first death in group 1:

$$p(s) = \frac{7!}{5! 1!} (s - 0)^5 (1 - s)^1 \quad (55)$$

$$p(t) = \frac{5!}{1! 3!} (t - 0)^1 (1 - t)^3 \quad (56)$$

$$\Pr(s \leq t) = \int_0^1 \int_0^t p(s) p(t) ds dt = 0.04545 \quad (57)$$

Figure S7: Graphical depictions of two orderings: (a) ***.**.** and (b) *****..**